

THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES IN INCREASING VOCABULARY RANGE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: In the given article the development of new information and communication effects on teaching vocabulary are discussed, as proper understanding of professional competence and quality in communication are very important and up to date issue.

Key words: ESL classes, matching words, guessing the definition, fill in the gaps, split vocabulary, ESL scrabble game, finding synonyms, antonyms, odd words, environmental problems.

Introduction 1.1

The study deals with the techniques of developing vocabulary skills in teaching ESL and we have full basis to approve that several linguistic scholars have brought the invaluable contribution to the study of teaching and learning vocabulary. According to the suggestion of a great linguist David Wilkins “Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed”. This is how the linguist proves the importance of vocabulary learning. If you spend most of your time studying grammar, your English will not improve very much. You will see most improvements if you learn more words and expressions. You can say very little with grammar, but you can say almost anything with words”. (Dollar H. and Hocking D., Innovations, LTP).

Material and methods 1.1.1

The advent of the communicative approach in the 1970s set the stage for a major re-think of the role of vocabulary. The communicative value of a core vocabulary has always been recognized, particularly by tourists. A phrase book or dictionary provides more communicative mileage than a grammar-in the short term at least. Recognition of the meaning –making potential of words meant that vocabulary became a learning objective in its own right. In 1984, for example in the introduction to their *Cambridge English course* Swan and Walter wrote that “Vocabulary acquisition is the largest and most important task facing the language learner”. Course books began to include activities that specifically targeted vocabulary.

Theory 1.1.2

According to the latest research works, which are given in the book “Teaching and learning vocabulary” I.S.P. Nation (1990), at present research on teaching and learning vocabulary is focusing on several areas, some of which continue previous research and some which break new ground. In the field of vocabulary learning goals researches have continued to look at the size and nature of the task facing learners, particularly in reading unsimplified texts. Laufer (1987) investigated the vocabulary coverage of text needed to make a significant difference to second language learners’ comprehension of the text. She found that a 95 percent vocabulary coverage had this effect while a 90 percent coverage did not. It shows that the effect of vocabulary size on coverage of academic texts finding that a 2000-headword vocabulary plus the University World list (Appendix 2) provides around 95 percent coverage of academic texts. If specialized word lists are not used the amount of vocabulary needed will be larger. Work in progress by Lauer (personal communication) provides experimental evidence that mastery of the 2000-3000 word level as measured by the levels test (see Appendix 8) is critical for comprehension of unsimplified texts.

Thus the primary grades may be characterized as overcoming a gap in word recognition, whereas the intermediate grades and beyond may be characterized as overcoming a gap in word meanings (Chall, 1987). Chall says that research evidence indicates that, for both word recognition and learning word meanings, direct teaching apart from context is a useful addition to contextual learning.

Results 1.1.3

Organizing vocabulary learning is also an important factor. According to the evidence presented by Crow (1986) and Crow and Quigley (1985) using a semantic field approach is very productive for the superior achievement in vocabulary learning. Other supporters of this kind of approach (Harvey, 1983; Maiguasha, 1984; Stieglits, 1983) have drawn on evidence from recall experiments in verbal learning studies and word association studies. However, much caution is needed in applying the findings of these studies to second language teaching. There are two reasons for this. First, the verbal learning studies have investigated recall of words that are already part of the subject’ vocabulary. There is a very big difference between recall of known items and learning new items. Words that are closely related to each other are easier to recall than unrelated words, but as Higa (1963) has shown, some kind of relationships help learning and some have a very strong negative effect on learning. Second, the word association studies look at the result of learning and language use.

Discussion 1.1.4

The importance of modern techniques in developing vocabulary skills of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) learners can be defined by the following reasons:

(1) Teachers want their students to be able to use the vocabulary communicatively. In order to do this, they believe students need to enlarge their lexis and to learn to use it automatically without stopping to think.

(2) Language learning is a process of habit formation. The more often something is repeated, the stronger the habits and the greater the learning. We must do lots of practices to be able to use vocabulary in a certain language. But in fact, most of students have little opportunity to practice using English outside the classroom. So they need lots of practices when they are in the classroom.

(3) to improve the quality of teaching techniques in vocabulary learning.

(4) to develop the students' vocabulary skills.

The purpose of the study consists in finding effective techniques for training of vocabulary Achievement of the effective purpose makes the decision on the following tasks:

1. to learn language by means of various techniques
2. to consider the main definitions of English vocabulary

The following techniques can be considered as supportive ones in teaching new vocabulary for ESP Learners:

1. Learning Vocabulary with pictures.

Procedure: Students try to describe the attached pictures on board

Students try to guess the topic of the lesson. They create their personal dictionaries on the topic.

Effectiveness: Students are encouraged to enlarge the vocabulary on the topic by working with pictures, which helps to memorize the vocabulary and develop their speaking skills.

Contributor: Devi Spencer, Language and Culture Center of the University of Houston

2. Matching exercises.

Procedure: Students try to find the suitable pairs for the given task

They match the word on the right to the correct definition on the left

Effectiveness: Students enjoy learning vocabulary as they have options for answers. It really eliminates "the dictionary panic" of learners.

Contributor: Richard Dean, Language Centre, Japan.

3. Words in Popular Music.

Procedure: Students listen the famous song in which some words related the topics are missed. They enjoy listening the song and write the appropriate vocabulary.

Effectiveness: Students develop the listening skills and at the same time they enrich the vocabulary by writing them in the given spaces.

Contributor: Coleman South, American Language Center, Damascus

By generalizing ideas about vocabulary learning let us think about again "What does it mean to "know" a vocabulary item? One way to answer this question is to try to clarify everything a learner has to do to acquire a vocabulary item. Richards (1976) outlined a series of assumptions about vocabulary ability that developed out of linguistic theory:

1. Knowing a word means knowing the degree of probability of encountering that word in speech or print. For many words we also "know" the sort of words most likely to be found associated with the word.
2. Knowing a word implies knowing the limitations imposed on the use of the word according to variations of function and situation.
3. Knowing a word means knowing the syntactic behavior associated with that word.

Conclusion 1.1.5

Concluding it should be noted that English language teachers should give vocabulary a high profile in the syllabus and in classroom activities so that students can understand its importance (O'Del, 1997). According to lexical approach, in which the words have a primary role, "to know a word means how to use it in the real life to be able to communicate" (Lewis, 1993). This means that proper vocabulary learning demands the productive use of vocabulary. The acquisition of vocabulary is also the most critical component of successful language learning in ESP. Certainly, vocabulary plays an important role in learning English. Learning and knowing a new word does not simply mean to understand its meaning, but also means to be able to use it properly for communicational aims in real life situations (Lewis, 1993). The ability of choosing appropriate techniques for ESP learners mostly depends on teacher's organization of plan and steps of reaching goals in teaching and learning vocabulary.

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